

HUMANITY SPACE
INTERNATIONAL ALMANAC

ГУМАНИТАРНОЕ ПРОСТРАНСТВО
МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ АЛЬМАНАХ

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Ю. Сухого-Алине
окр. пос. Соколычи
из лич. Н.К. Тилля
23. VII. 1980 С. Мурзин

Miaenia tiliae
sp. nov. **TYPE**
Det. S. Murzin 1981

HOLOTYPE
Miaenia "
TILIAE sp. n.
S. Murzin det. 1981

Зоомузей МГУ (Москва, РОССИЯ)
№ ZMMU Col 02982
Zool. Mus. Mosc. Univ.
(Mosque, ROSSIA)
ex coll. S. V. Murzin

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Фото на обложке / Cover photo: *Terinaea tiliae* (Murzin, 1983):

Holotype, female (length: 6.0 mm; width: 1.8 mm) with 4 labels: 1) “South of Sikhote-Alin /

near the village of Sokolchi / from the personal p / c Tilia / 23.VII.1980 S. Murzin” [in

Russian]; 2) [white] “Miaenia tiliae / sp.nov. Typus / Det. S.Murzin 1981”; 3) [red]

“HOLOTYPUS / Miaenia / TILIAE sp.n. / S.Murzin det. 1981”; 4) [pink] “Zoomuseum of

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**The subspecies taxonomy of *Dorcadion (Cribrodorcadion) lugubre*
Kraatz, 1873 and *D. (C.) etruscum* (Rossi, 1790)
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, *Dorcadion*, taxonomy, distribution, name restored, status new, synonym new, lectotypes, paralectotypes.

Abstract: The subspecies structure of *Dorcadion lugubre* Kraatz, 1873 and *D. etruscum* (Rossi, 1790) is revised. *D. lugubre* is accepted as monotypic, without subspecies. *D. etruscum* is accepted with 6 subspecies: *D. e. etruscum*; *D. e. johannisfranci* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007, **stat. nov.**, *D. e. salonicum* Pic, 1916, **stat. rest.**, *D. e. epirense* Breuning, 1942 **stat. nov.**, *D. e. valonense* Pic, 1917; *D. e. bravardi* Pic, 1916. New synonyms are proposed: *D. lugubre* Kraatz, 1873 = *D. thessalicum* Pic, 1916 = *D. minkovae* Heyrovský, 1962 = *D. meteorum* Breuning, 1969 = *D. parinfernale* Breuning, 1975, **syn. nn.**, *D. e. salonicum* Pic, 1916, **stat. rest.** = *D. pelionense* Breit, 1923 = *D. ariannae* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2008, **syn. nn.**, *D. e. epirense* Breuning, 1942 **stat. nov.** = *D. kozanii* Breuning, 1962 (= *D. k. daccordii* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007) = *D. tassii* Breuning, 1964 = *D. pindicum* Breuning, 1966, **syn. nn.**, *D. e. bravardi* Pic, 1916 = *D. albosuturale* Breuning, 1962, **syn. nov.** A lectotype of *Dorcadion femoratum* v. *apulum* Depoli, 1926 is designated.

Introduction

According to Danilevsky (2020), *D. lugubre* Kraatz, 1873 widely distributed in Europe includes 5 subspecies: *D. l. lugubre* Kraatz, 1873 (= *discosulcatum* Pic, 1926a = *pseudolugubre* Breuning, 1943 = *salonicum* Pic, 1916 = *sparsepilosum* Pic, 1926b) known from Bulgaria, Greece, and Macedonia, *D. l. meteorum* Breuning, 1969 from Central Greece, *D. l. minkovae* Heyrovský, 1962 from Bulgaria, *D. l. parinfernale* Breuning, 1975 (= *giachinoi* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007) from Northern Greece, *D. l. thessalicum* Pic, 1916 (= *pelionense* Breit, 1923) from Greece. Five species were also accepted: *D. albosuturale* Breuning, 1962 (Albania, Greece,

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Macedonia), *D. bravardi* Pic, 1916 (Albania, Greece, Macedonia), *epirensis* Breuning, 1942 (Greece), *D. johannisfranci* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007 (Greece, Turkey) and *D. valonense* Pic, 1917 (= *apfelbecki* Winkler, 1929 = *valonense* Apfelbeck, 1923) from Albania.

D. etruscum (Rossi, 1790) consists of two Italian subspecies: *D. e. etruscum* (Rossi, 1790) and *D. e. fiorii* Breuning, 1942.

New taxonomy of the group is proposed.

Material and method

Material was collected manually. Specimens used in morphological studies were killed by ethyl acetate. All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Acronyms of collections:

AG - collection of A.I. Gubin (Donetsk)

IP - collection of I.G. Pljushtch (Kiev)

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow)

ML - collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow)

YuS - collection of Yu.E. Skrylnyk (Kharkiv)

SM - collection of S.V. Murzin (Moscow)

ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow University

Results

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lugubre Kraatz, 1873

Dorcadion lugubre Kraatz, 1873: 41 - "Macedonien, bei Salonick"; Oertzen, 1886: 286 - "Thessl."; Breit, 1923: 148, 149 - "Saloniki, Keretschkoi, Mazedonien"; Heyrovský, 1967: 579, 610, part. - "Mazedonien, Albanien, Griechenland, Bulgarien", "Tomor, Kloster Abbas-Ali, 1800 m"; Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 135 - Yug.-Makedonia: "Stari Dojran", Makedonia (central): "Kilkis, Dorcas"; Behne & Gaedike, 2013: 184 - "Salonick" (Syntype).

Dorcadion thessalicum Pic, 1916: 22 - "Thessalie" (wrong locality, see Braun, 1978 and Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2010); Heyrovský, 1967: 579 - "Griechenland"; Braun, 1978: 115 - "Graec. bor. Pangaion Akrovounion", "Pangaion Platanotopos". **syn. nov.**

Dorcadion (s. str.) *lugubre*, Aurivillius, 1922: 36.

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- Dorcadion lugubre* v. *sparsepilosum* Pic, 1926b: 13 - "Environs de Salonique".
- Dorcadion pseudolugubre* Breuning, 1943: 96 - "Macédoine: Karatschköi"; Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 135 - Macedonia (east): "Kavala, Likostomo, Limnia".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) lugubre* m. *densepilosum* Breuning, 1946: 114 - "Salonique, Grèce".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) lugubre*, Breuning, 1962: 353 - "Macedonien: Mt. Elias, Karatschköj, Makana Polje, Bejalsnica Planina, Mts. Alibotus etc.; Thessalien: Satel südlich Kozani; Bulgarien: Kresna Défilé"; Mikšić & Korpič, 1985: 42 - "Makedonija, Tesalija, Bugarska"; "Makedonija: Demirkapija, Kotrišnica, Valandovo"; Pesarini & Sabbadini 2010: 182, 183 (= *D. salonicum* Pic) - "Grecia: Serres (Kalokastro, Kefalohori) e Calcidica (Polygyros)" (Lectotype male - figs 3, 31 - "un sintipo ♂ etichettato "Salonik").
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) minkovae* Heyrovský, 1962: 225 - "Kresna-Defilé, Bulgarisch-Mazedonien". **syn.nov.**
- Dorcadion minkovae*, Heyrovský, 1967: 579 - "Bulgarien".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) meteorum* Breuning, 1969: 42 - "Grèce, Kalabaka, région des Météores". **syn. nov.**
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) meteorum* m. *leucosuturale* Breuning, 1969: 42 - "Grèce, Kalabaka, région des Météores".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) parinfernale* Breuning, 1975: 10 - "Grèce: Kavalla"; Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2010: 183, 184 - "Macedonia orientale, nomo di Kavala e nomo di Xanthi, negli immediati dintorni di Kavala, sembri particolarmente abbondante soprattutto sul massiccio del M. Lekani" - ("Lekani, Grecia (Greece), nomo Kavala"). **syn nov.**
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) pseudolugubre*, Mikšić & Korpič, 1985: 43 - "Makedonija (Kartšoi, Petrič)".
- Dorcadion (Carnatorcadion) minkovae*, Mikšić & Korpič, 1985: 47 - "Bugarska".
- Dorcadion meteorum*, Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 135 - Thessaly: "Meteora".
- Dorcadion albosuturale*, Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 135, part. - Macedonia (west): "Olympos".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) thessalicum thessalicum*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: 43, part. (= *D. metrorum* Breuning, 1969 - as "nomen nudum") - "5 km S Vlahava, Grecia (Greece), nom. Trikala", "nella regione delle Meteore"; Plewa et al., 2011: 237, 245 "Trikala: 5 km N od miejscowości Meteora; Ftiotyda: Pindos Mts.; Larisa: Olimp Mts. 1200 m"; Danilevsky, 2010a: 254 - Greece.
- Pedestredorcadion lugubre*, Migliaccio et al., 2007: 45, part. - "Macedonia, Bulgaria, Albania"; along Struma valley in Bulgaria.
- Pedestredorcadion minkovae*, Migliaccio et al., 2007: 46, part. - "Bulgaria", Kresna.
- Pedestredorcadion pseudolugubre*, Migliaccio et al., 2007: 46, part. - "Bulgaria", Petrich.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) thessalicum giachinoi* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: 45, 72, 79 - "Grecia, nom Karditsa: Oros Karava"; Danilevsky, 2010a: 254 - Greece.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) thessalicum thessalicum*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2010: 183 (= *D. pseudolugubre* Breuning, 1943) - "dalle province di Pella

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- (Notia) e Kilkis (Fanos) e dalla porzione occidentale di quella di Kavala (2 kmW Podohori)".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) pseudolugubre*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 251 - Bulgaria, Greece, Macedonia.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) salonicum*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 252 - Greece, Macedonia.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lugubre*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 249, part. - Albania, Bulgaria, Greece, Macedonia; Aistleitner et al., 2015: 545 - "Bulgarien, Sandansk"; "Kresna Gorge".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) minkovae*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 250 - Bulgaria.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) parinfernale*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 251 - Greece.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lugubre minkovae*, Danilevsky, 2014: 252 - "Bulgaria, Struma valley"; 2020: 350 - Bulgaria.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lugubre lugubre*, Danilevsky, 2020: 350 - ?Bulgaria, Greece, Macedonia.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lugubre thessalicum*, Danilevsky, 2020: 350 - "GR (Pella: Notia - 41°6'6"N, 22°12'30"E e Kilkis: Fanos - 41°4'46"N, 22°28'39"E)".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lugubre parinfernale*, Danilevsky, 2020: 350 - Greece (Kavala).
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lugubre meteorum*, Danilevsky, 2020: 350 - Greece.

Type locality. North-Eastern Greece, Saloniki environs, according to the original description.

Pronotum and elytra with very dense rough puncturation, without white central line; antennae and legs totally black; elytral puncturation from very dense with interspaces between dots less than their diameter to rather sparse and very scattered; elytra could be wider or narrower; the smallest male in available materials have body length 12.7 mm and width 4.8 mm (Lekani); the biggest male has body length 18.1 mm and width 6.7 mm (Pangaion Mt.); the smallest female (Sandanski env.) in available materials have body length 14.9 mm and width 5.8 mm; the biggest female (Larisa) has body length 21.4 mm and width 8.7 mm.

Material. 1 female with two labels: 1) "Saloniki / IV.1919 / (Macedonia) / L. Sheljushko leg. / coll. L. Sheljushko"; 2) "*Dorcadion* / ?*hedwigae* Jur." - SM; 1 male, Bulgaria, Sandanski, Dr. Sobota / *Dorcadion lugubre* det. S. Kadlec - SM; 1 male, 1 female, Bulgaria mer., Sandanski, 6.1967, E. Lekeš - SM; 1 male, Bulgaria mer. occ., Sandanski (Liljanovo), 5.-10.6.1976, Karel Majer

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leg. - SM; 1 male, Bulgaria, Sandanski, 8.5.1986, Sobota leg. / *Dorcadion lugubre* det. S. Kadlec - SM; 1 female, Bulgaria, env. Melnik, 20.5.1980, J. Volak leg. / *Dorcadion lugubre* det. S. Kadlec - SM; 1 male, Bulgaria, Kosuch, 17.5.1983, J. Canev leg. - SM; 2 males, 1 female, Greece CE, W of Larisa, Zarkos env., 9.5.2014, Snižek leg. - SM; 1 male, Belasica Pl., Bulg. Mac., Dr. Purkyně - ZMM [as "*Dorcadion salonicum*"]; 3 males, 3 females, YU Mt. Belasica, 1200 m, Džami Kran, 11.5.1988, I. Toševski - MD; 1 male, "GR Makedonia / Palaea Kavalla / Kavala 7.4.1985 / B. Drovenik - SM"; 1 male, 1 female, Lekani-Kavala (Macedonia, Grecia), 700 m, 6.2000, Etonti leg. - SM; 2 males, 1 female, NE Greece, Pangaion Mt., 1550-1600 m, near Ski center, 40.906N, 24.102 E, 29.4.2018, T. Zhura, S. Murzin leg. - SM; 6 males, 2 females, Greece, nomos Kavala, Pangaion Mt., 500-800 m, on the road to the Ski center, 29-30.4.2018, S. Murzin leg. - SM; 4 males, 2 females, Greece, nomos Kavala, Podochori vill env., 300 m, - 40°50'11.57"N, 24°01'56.13"E, 3.5.2018, S. Murzin leg. - SM; 3 males, 3 females, GR, Makedonia, Pal. Kavala, 550 m, 3.5.1984, O. Krätschmer - MD [as "*Dorcadion parinfernale*"]; 2 males, Grecia, Makedonia, Lekani/Kavala, 800 m, 18.6.1992, M. Etonti - MD [as "*Dorcadion parinfernale*"]; 2 males, GR, Macedonia, Lekani, 760 m, 2.5.2014, S. Dementiev, T. Repina - MD [as "*Dorcadion parinfernale*"]; 1 female, Melnik, 11.5.1967, P. Angelov - MD [as "*Dorcadion minkovae*"]; 1 male, 1 female, Kresna defile, 22.5.1970, P. Angelov - MD [as "*Dorcadion minkovae*"]; 1 male, 1 female, Bulg. m., Sandanski, 7.6.1972, K. Poláček leg. - MD [as "*Dorcadion minkovae*"]; 1 male, Bulg. occ. mer., Sandanski, 30.5.-1.6.1984, Dr. M. Real - MD [as "*Dorcadion minkovae*"]; 2 females, Bulgaria, Kresna, 12.5.1988, V. Sakalyan - MD [as "*Dorcadion minkovae*"]; 2 males, SW Bulgaria, Sandanski-Petrich Valley, 23.4.1992, V. Sakalyan - MD [as "*Dorcadion minkovae*"]; 4 male, 3 females, Bulgaria, Sandanski, 21.5.1999, J. Kurzava MD [as "*Dorcadion minkovae*"]; 1 male, 1 female, Gr (Mak.) Pangaion, E. Podochorion, 3.4.1986, Krätschmer - MD [as "*Dorcadion pseudolugubre*"]; 1 female, Grecia, Olympo Mt., 1300 m, 28.4.1981, R.Mourglia - SM [as "*Dorcadion albosaturale*"]; 1 male, GR, Olymp, Ski Center, 1300 m, 29.5.1988, Krätschmer - SM [as "*Dorcadion albosaturale*"]; 1 male, 1 female, Grece, Kastraki-Meteora, 13.5.2012, Dr. B. Bubenik - ML [as "*Dorcadion*

meteorum”]; 3 males, 1 female, GR (Trikkala), Meteora, 350 m, (ca 2 km ne Kalambaka), 24.4.1990, Heinz - MD [as “*Dorcadion meteorum*”].

Distribution. The species is widely distributed in Balkan Region: North Macedonia (south-east part of the country near Bulgaria and Greece border: Demir-kapija, Kotrišnica, Valandovo); Bulgaria Struma river basin; Greece: Macedonia and Thrace, Thessaly and Central Greece, Epirus and Western Macedonia.

The record of *Dorcadion lugubre* from - “Sivas: Karayün village, 1440 m” by Özdikmen (2004) was based on wrong identification.

Remark. *Dorcadion thessalicum* Pic was described from “Thessalie” on the base of a single totally black glabrous female. All related taxa from Greece have very similar rather variable females. So, the definition of the type locality by different authors was rather different. A group of authors accepted Mt. Pelion as its type locality (Breuning, 1962; Steiner, 2003). Other authors placed the type locality near Meteora in Central Greece. According to Braun, 1978, it was situated in North-Eastern Greece not far from Kavala. That opinion was shared by Pesarini & Sabbadini (2010) and was published in the new Cerambycidae Palaearctic Catalogue (Danilevsky, 2020). That position is accepted by me.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum* (Rossi, 1790)**

Lamia pedestris Rossi 1790: 146 - “in provinciis Florentina et Pisana” (misapplied).

Lamia molitor etrusca Rossi, 1790: 147 - “in provinciis Florentina et Pisana”.

? *Dorcadion femoratum* Brullé, 1832: 259 - “Morée”.

? *Dorcadion nudum* Küster, 1852: 93 - “In Ungarn ?”

Dorcadion (s. str.) *etruscum*, Aurivillius, 1922: 34, 43, part. - Italien; Winkler, 1929: 1191, part. - “Italia”.

Dorcadion etruscum, Sama, 1984: 4 - “Toscana” (neotype designation).

Type locality. Italy, Toscana (according to the neotype designation by Sama, 1984).

Body, antennae and legs totally black or partly reddish; pronotum and elytra usually with less rough puncturation than in *D. lugubre*; pronotum and elytra in males always glabrous; without ground pubescence; pronotum and elytral suture with narrow white

line often indistinct or obliterated, never followed by velvety-black stripes; females often with densely pubescent elytra; dirty-white dorsal, lateral and marginal pale stripes can be distinct, as well as sutural white stripes; body length in males: 10.2-17.1 mm, body width: 3.6-6.5 mm, body length in females: 12.0-19.2 mm, body width: 4.0-7.6 mm.

Distribution. Whole Italy, from the northern provinces to Sicilia; Balkan territories: Albania, Greece, Bulgaria.

Six subspecies are accepted.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum etruscum (Rossi, 1790)

Lamia pedestris Rossi 1790: 146 - "in provinciis Florentina et Pisana", (misapplied).

Lamia molitor etrusca Rossi, 1790: 147 - "in provinciis Florentina et Pisana".

Dorcadion italicum Küster, 1847: 99 - "Italien".

Dorcadion femoratum, Kraatz, 1873: 56, part. - "Griechenland, Lombardei bis Sicilien. Piemont, Toscana, Monte Senario, Pratolino, Rom, Neapel, Camaldoli, Sicilien".

? *Dorcadion fuscifrons* Chevrolat, 1882: 60 - "Albania" ("Abruzzen" sensu supposition by Breuning, 1962).

Dorcadion femoratum v. *subiacum* Pic, 1917a: 10 - "Italie: Subiaco".

Dorcadion femoratum v. *romanorum* Pic, 1917b: 7 - "Italie".

Dorcadion femoratum v. *etruscum*, Depoli, 1926: 25 - "Toscana".

Dorcadion femoratum v. *apulium* Depoli, 1926: 25 - "Puglia, Basilicata"; Breuning, 1942: 126, 128 - "Apulien".

Dorcadion femoratum v. *apenninum* Depoli, 1926: 25 - "Emilia, Marche, Abruzzi".

Dorcadion femoratum v. *siculum* Depoli, 1926: 27 - "Sicilia (Ficuzza)".

Dorcadion calabricum Breuning, 1942: 127, 128 - "Calabrien".

Dorcadion etruscum, Breuning, 1942: 126, 128 - "Südtalien, Sizilien"; Parenti & Tassi, 1964: 34 (= *femoratum* Brullé) "Le Cese, Colle dei Gati, Colli Merini, Logo Barea"; Sama & Schurmann, 1980: 213 - "Lombardia, Veneto, Emilia, Romagna, Toscana, Umbria, Lazio, Marche, Puglia, Lucania (?), Sicilia", "Ficuzza, Madonie (R); Messina; Nebrodi: Floresta, Randazzo"; Sama, 1984: 4 - "Toscana" (Neotype); 1988: 131 (= *D. f. apulium*, = *D. fiorii*, = *D. calabricum*) - "Italia continentale, Sicilia"; Fabbri & Hernández, 1996: 20, part - "Italia continentale, Sicilia, Albania e Grecia." (Biology); Contarini, 2014: 49 - "Parco Naturale della Vena del Gesso romagnola", "Monticino di Brisighella, M. del Casino, Tossignano".

Dorcadion fiorii Breuning, 1942: 126, 128 - "Südtalien, Calabrei, Cotronei".

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) femoratum m. *apiceseparatum* Breuning, 1946: 114 - "Cerchio, Italie".

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) femoratum m. *obscurevittatum* Breuning, 1946: 114 - "Castel di Sangro, Italie".

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- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) apulum m. pugliense* Breuning, 1956: 723 - “Apulie“, (nomen nudum).
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) etruscum*, Breuning, 1962: 345, part. - “Über Mitellitalien, Süditalien (ohne Apulien), Sizilien, Albanien, Insel Korfu und das westliche Griechenland (Epirus und West-Morea) verbreitet”; Sama & Rapuzzi, 2011: 140, part. - Italy: Abruzzo, Basilicata, Calabria, Campania, Emilia, Lazio, Lombardia, Marche, Piemonte, Puglia, Romagna, Sicilia, Toscana, Umbria, Veneto; Luna & Rapuzzi, 2016: 187 - Italia, Umbria Region, Perugia Province: “Foligno, Cancelli, 900 m”, “Trevi, monte Brunette, 1400 m”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) etruscum m. romanorum*, Breuning, 1962: 347 “Latium, Umgebung Rom; Basilicata: serino; Livorno”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) fiorii*, Breuning, 1962: 349 - “Süditalien, Calabrien, Cotrone und Catanzaro”; Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1995: 48 - “Calabria”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) fiorii m. etruscifforme* Breuning, 1962: 349 - “Calabrien, Catanzaro”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) apulum*, Breuning, 1962: 348 - “Süditalien: Umgebung Bari”; “Gioia di Colle”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) calabricum*, Breuning, 1962: 348 - “in Apulien bei San Basilio und Grottaglie”; wrong locality: “Süditalien: Calabrien, Antonimina”.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) calabricum m. apulense* Breuning, 1962: 349 - “Apulien: Grottaglie”.
- Pedestredorcadion etruscum*, Usvelli, 2003: 59 - “Badia della Valle, Marradi (Firenze)”; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2006: 170 - Sicilia; Rapuzzi & Kairouz, 2010: 174 - “Toscane, Italie”.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum etruscum*, Özdikmen, 2010: 430 - Italy, Sicily; Danilevsky, 2010a: 246, part. - Italy; 2020: 345, part. - Italy; Sakalian et al., 2020: 66 - “Italia: Abruzzo, Lazio and Molise National Park”; 2021: 53 - “Italy: Monte Sirente”.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum fiorii*, Özdikmen, 2010: 430 - S Italy; Danilevsky, 2010a: 247 - Italy; 2020: 346 - Italy.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) etruscum*, Sama & Rapuzzi, 2011: 140, part. - Italy: Abruzzo, Basilicata, Calabria, Campania, Emilia, Lazio, Lombardia, Marche, Piemonte, Puglia, Romagna, Sicilia, Toscana, Umbria, Veneto.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum*, Baviera et al., 2017: 45 - Italy, Sicily: “Messina: Monti Nebrodi, Bosco di San Fratello; Catania: Monti Nebrodi Lago Trearie; Enna: Troina; Palermo: Madonie, Isnello; Geraci Siculo, Portella Mandarinini”; PetruzzIELLO & Migliorini, 2019: 170 - “Piacenza, 60 m”, “Piacenza, I Vaccari, 75 m”.
- Dorcadion etruscum etruscum*, Angelini, 2020: 189 - Italy: “Apulia, Basilicata and Calabria”, “Gargano Promontory, Policoro Wood, Pantano Lake of Pignola, M. Vulture Monticchio L., Central Lucan Apennines, Pollino Massif, Sila Plateau, Aspromonte”.

Type locality. Italy, Toscana (according to the neotype designation by Sama, 1984).

Legs and 1st antennal joint dark-red or nearly black; pronotum regularly convex, with very dense puncturation; thoracic lateral spines usually longer, than in other subspecies; male elytra usually glabrous; sutural and pronotal narrow white stripes usually followed by hardly distinct wide stripes of black pubescence; sometimes similar black pubescence can be seen near elytral middle; curved elytral margin usually with dense pubescence getting denser along epipleurae; female elytra with fine dark pubescence; pale elytral dorsal stripes more or less distinct; body length in males: 11.5-16.0 mm, body width: 3.8-6.4 mm, body length in females: 12.0-17.0 mm, body width: 4.0-7.2 mm.

Material. 2 males, 2 females, Italia, Reitter - ZMM; 2 males, Italia, v. Bodemeyer - ZMM; 1 female, Toscana (FI), Pratolino, M. Agini - MD; 1 male, S. Basilio - ZMM; 1 male with three labels: 1) "S. Basilio / Murgien", 2) "*Dorcadion / calabricum* / det. Breuning", 3) "*etruscum* / det. M. Danilevsky 19__" - ZMM; 1 female with three labels: 1) [red] "COTYPE", 2) "S. Basilio / Murgien", 3) "*Dorcadion / calabricum* / det. Breuning" - ZMM; 3 males, 3 females, San Basilio, Murgie, Paganetti leg. - ZMM; 2 males, Italia, Murgien - MD; 2 males, Italia, Roma, 15.4.1960, Migliaccio - SM; 1 female, Italy, Roma, Vitinia, XI.1954, Saca. - ZMM; 1 male with two labels: 1) "Italien / Reitter. Leder.", 2) Abruzzen / Reitter - ZMM; 1 female, Abruzzen, Paganetti leg. - ZMM; 2 males, Abruzzo - MD; 1 male, Italia, Abruzzo, 5.1960, G. Sama - SM; 1 male, Lazio, Roma, 15.4.1960, E. Migliaccio - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Italia, Romagna, Cezena, 19.3.1974, Dr. Schurmann - MD; 1 male, Italia, Calabria, Sibari, 6.5.1975, R. Mourglia - MD; 1 male, Italia, Puglie, M. S. Angelo, 5.1977, D.G. Anasso - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Emilia R., BO, Casaleccio R., 5.6.1987, 22.4.1979, G. Zappi - MD; 1 female, Emilia R. (BO) Sasso Marconi, t. Setta, 2.6.1987, G. Zappi - MD; 1 male, Lombardia - ZMM; 1 female, Italia, Sicilia, Monte Soro (1700), 26.4.1981, Contarini - SM.

Lectotype of *Dorcadion femoratum* v. *apulium* Depoli, 1926 (Figs 1), present designation, male (length: 15.5 mm, width: 6,4 mm)

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with five labels: 1) “Bari / 18.5.25 / Shatzmayr”, 2) “femoratum / apulum m. / G. Depoli det.”, 3) “*Dorc. etrusc. / apulum / Museo P. Rossi*”, 4) LECTOTYPUS / *Dorcadion / femoratum v. APULUM / Depoli, 1926 / M.Lazarev des., 2023*, 5) “Зоомузей МГУ (Москва, РОССИЯ) / № ZMMU Col 03045 / Zool. Mus. Mosq. Univ. / (Mosquae, ROSSIA) / ex coll. N. N. Plavilstshikov” - ZMM. 3 paralectotypes, present designation; 3 males from same locality and with same data - ZMM.

Distribution. About whole Apennine Peninsula and Sicily Island.

Remark. The Italian subspecies is extremely geographically variable. The existence of many local subspecies is quite evident, but the exact delimitation of the Italian taxa is a future problem.

Fig 1. *D. (C.) e. etruscum* (Rossi, 1790), male, lectotype of *D. femoratum v. apulum* Depoli, 1926 with labels.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum johannisfranci*
Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007, stat. nov.**

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) lugubre, Önalp, 1990: 70, part. - “Amasya”;
“Türkiye, Trakya”.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) johannisfranci Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: 40, 72, 79
- “Grecia, Tracia, nom. Evros: Monastiraki; nom. Evros: Ardani; nom.
Evros: Likofos; nom. Evros: 5 km N Didimotikho; nom. Evros: Mani; nom.
Evros: 1 km S Feres; nom. Evros: Feres; Turchia europaea, Edirne.”;
Danilevsky, 2010a: 248 - Greece, Turkey; 2020: 348 - Greece, Turkey.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lugubre, Özdikmen, 2010: 445, part. - Amasya prov.;
Sivas prov.; Thracia (European Turkey).

Type locality. Greece, Thrace, Nomos Evros, Monastiraki.

Legs and 1st antennal joint reddish; pronotum regularly convex with shallow central depression, with scattered bigger dots and narrow central white line; lateral thoracic spines short and sharp; elytra usually glabrous and shining; narrow sutural white stripes never followed by black pubescence; poor traces of pale humeral stripes are visible near elytral apices; curved elytral margin without pale pubescence; marginal white stripes limited by epipleurae; body length in males: 10.2-14.5 mm, body width: 3.6-5.3 mm, body length in females: 12.5-17.6 mm, body width: 5.0-7.4 mm.

Distribution. Eastern border of Greek Thrakia along Turkish border (Nomos Evros), western margin of Turkish Thrakia (Edirne).

Material. 1 female, Greece, 2 km S Dadia, Evros distr., 26.4.2011 - SM; 4 males, GR, Thraki, Karoti-Mani, 26.4.2012, V. Skoupý - MD; 7 males, 2 females, Greece, E Macedonia, Monastiraki, 4-5.5.2014, 12-13.4.2016, S. Dementiev, T. Repina - MD.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum salonicum* Pic, 1916, stat. rest.**

Dorcadion salonicum Pic, 1916: 22 - “Environs de Salonique”; 1917b: 7 -
“Salonique”; Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 135 - Makedonia (central):
“Kalokastro”.

Dorcadion pelionense Breit, 1923: 145, 148, 149 - “Gipfelregion des Pelion in
Thessalien”; Behne & Gaedike, 2013: 188 - “Thessalien, Pelion”
(Syntype). **syn. nov.**

Dorcadion salonicum v. *discosulcatum* Pic, 1926a: 1 - “Macédoine”.

Dorcadion (s. str.) *salonicum*, Winkler, 1929: 1191 - “Saloniki”.

Dorcadion (s. str.) *thessalicum*, Winkler, 1929: 1191 - “Thessal.”.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) thessalicum, Breuning, 1958: 21 - “Thessalie”;

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- 1962: 354 (= *pilionense* Breit, 1923) - "Mt. Pelion"; Steiner, 2003: 153 - "Mt. Pelion".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) thessalicum*, Breuning, 1962: 354 - "Thessalien, MT. Pelion".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) salonicum*, Breuning, 1962: 354 - "Macedonien: Gorgol, Ostrova See; Bjelasica Planina; Kaimakcalan".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) albosuturale* m. *completevittipenne* Breuning, 1962: 352 - "Kozani, Thessalien, 1700 m".
- Dorcadion thessalicum*, Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 134 - Thessaly: "Mt. Pelio".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) thessalicum pelionense*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: 45, 72, 79 - "M. Pelio e M. Ossa"; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 254 - Greece.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum bravardi*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: 47, 48, 72, 79, part - "Tessaglia e Macedonia", "nomo Larisa (M. Ossa 3 km a Est di Spilia), n. Grevena (Anixi), n. Kozani (M. Vourinos presso Paleokastro), n. Pella (M. Paiko) e n. Florina (3 km a Est di Vevi, K1idio)".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) ariannae* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2008: 115 - "Grecia, nom. Xanthi, Petrohori"; Danilevsky, 2010a: 252 - Greece; 2020: 341 - Greece. **syn. nov.**

Type locality. Greece, Saloniki environs.

Legs and 1st antennal joint red or reddish; pronotum regularly convex with shallow central depression, with scattered bigger dots and narrow central white line; lateral thoracic spines short and sharp; elytra usually glabrous and shining; narrow sutural white stripes never followed by black pubescence; humeral stripes never visible apically; curved elytral margin with pale pubescence slightly wider than epipleurae; females androchromal; body length in males: 16.4-17.1 mm, width: 5.9-6.5 mm; body length in females: 14.8-19.2 mm, body width: 6.5-7.6 mm.

The taxon differs from closely relative *D. e. epirense* by bigger size, rather distinct white pronotal and sutural elytral stripes, denser elytral puncturation.

Material. 1 male, Gr., Domenikon, 4.1972, W.Heinz - MD; 1 female, Graecia, Mac. c., Kalokastron 31.5.1981 J. & M. Sláma - MD; 5 males, Greece, Ossa Mt., 367 m, 39°46'02"N, 22°35'52"E, 30.4.2017, V. Gazanchidis - MD [as "*Dorcadion pelionense*"]

Distribution. Greece, Central Macedonia (Chalkidiki peninsula with northern environs) and southwards to about southern Thessaly.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum epirense* Breuning, 1942,
stat. nov.**

- Dorcadion epirense* Breuning, 1942: 128 - "Griechenland: Epirus, Cumerka Massiv, Kataphigi"; Heyrovský, 1967: 579, part. - "Albanien, Griechenland"; Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 135 - Greece: "Aetolia: Stavros, Agrinio".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) epirense* m. *apicefasciatum* Breuning, 1946: 114 - "Kataphigi, Epire".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) epirense* m. *invittatum* Breuning, 1946: 114 - "Kataphigi, Epire".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) kozanii* Breuning, 1962: 318 - "Sattel südlich Kozani, Mazedonian, 1600 m". **syn. nov.**
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) kozanii* m. *larissae* Breuning, 1962: 319 - "Larissa, Thessalien".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) kozanii* m. *pseudolarissae* Breuning, 1962: 319 - "Larissa, Thessalien".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) kozanii* m. *discoCompletum* Breuning, 1962: 319 - "Larissa, Thessalien".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) epirense*, Breuning, 1962: 349 - "Griechenland: Epirus, Mt. Cumerka, Kataphigi, 1200-1400 m".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) tassii* Breuning, 1964: 32 - "Grèce, entre Jannina et Metsovo, près du village Megalo Peristeri". **syn. nov.**
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) pindicum* Breuning, 1966: 4 - "Grèce: Mt. Pinde, Mazia". **syn. nov.**
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) pindicum* m. *cassolai* Breuning, 1966: 5 - "Grèce: Mt. Pinde, Mazia".
- Dorcadion etruscum*, Heyrovský, 1967: 579, part. - "Albanien, Griechenland"; Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 135 - Kerkira (Corfu): "Aj. Mathaeos".
- Dorcadion tassii*, Heyrovský, 1967: 579 - "Griechenland".
- Dorcadion bravardi*, Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 135 - Makedonia (central): "Anthrakia".
- Dorcadion albosuturale*, Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 135, part. - Makedonia (west): "Olympos".
- Dorcadion tassi*, Sláma & Slámová, 1996: 135 - Epirus: "Ioánina".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) kozanii*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: 41, 42, 72, 79 - "Tessaglia e Macedonia meridionale".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) kozanii daccordii* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: 42, 72, 79 - "Grecia, Pindo centrale", "nom. Karditsa: Oros Karava"; "nom. Karditsa: Oros Voutsikaki"; nom. Ioanina: Metsovo"; nom. Grevena: Anixia"; Danilevsky, 2010a: 248 - Greece; 2020: 348 - Greece. **syn. nov.**
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) thessalicum thessalicum*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: 43, part. (= *D. meteorum* Breuning, 1969 - as "nomen nudum") - "5 km S Vlahava, Grecia (Greece), nom. Trikala", "nella regione delle Meteore"; Plewa et al., 2011: 237, 245 "Trikala: 5 km N od miejscowości Meteora; Ftiotyda: Pindos Mts.; Larisa: Olimp Mts. 1200 m".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum bravardi*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: 47, 72, 79, part. - "Tessaglia e Macedonia", "3 km E Spilia" [Mt. Ossa!].

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- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) epirensis*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 246 - Greece; 2020: 345 - Greece.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) kozanii kozanii*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 248 - Greece; 2020: 348 - Greece.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) pindicum*, Danilevsky, 2010a:251 - Greece; 2020: 353 - Greece.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) bravardi*, Plewa et al., 2011: 237 - Greece “Larisa: Olimp Mts. 1500 m”
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) tassii*, Danilevsky, 2020: 358 - Greece.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) etruscum*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004: 136 - “Peloponneso”.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum*, Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: 46, 72, 79 - “Pindo, Corfù e Peloponneso”.
- Dorcadion olympicum* v. *beieri* Pic: 1932, 18, - “Péloponnèse, Voïda”.

Type locality: Greece: Epirus, Mt. Cumerka, Kataphigi.

Males usually glabrous, elytra with white sutural stripe and narrow marginal stripes; or elytra sometimes with black pubescence along white sutural stripes; or elytra with dark pubescence and glabrous humeral and dorsal lines; females usually autochromal with dark-brown elytral pubescence and wide dirty white dorsal and humeral stripes; legs, 1st antennal joint and legs red or reddish; pronotum regularly convex, with very dense regular puncturation and narrow central white line; lateral thoracic spines short and sharp; body length in males: 11.0-14.6 mm, width: 4.5-5.4 mm; body length in females: 13.4-16.0 mm, body width: 6.2-6.5 mm.

Material. 1 male, 2 females, Graecia, N. Ioannina, Katarapaß, 1500 m, 5.5.1988, Steiner - MD [as “*Dorcadion tassii*”]; 2 males, 1 female, GR, Epirus, Ioannina, 4.5.1993, 21.4.1993, J. Macek - SM; 2 males, GR, Pindus, 18 km Ioannina, 950 m, 30.4.1983, Krätchmer - SM [as “*Dorcadion tassii*”]; 1 female, Grecia, Pindo, Katara - Metsovo mt., 1500 m, 25.4.1981, R. Mourglia MD [as “*Dorcadion tassii*”]; 4 males, 2 females, Grecia, Epiro, Hegoumeni dint, 19-20.4.1993, V. Skoupý - MD.

Distribution. Central Greece from Western Makedonia, Epirus and Thessaly to Peloponneso.

Remark. I don't know Peloponneso populations, so, I preliminary regard all inside *D. etruscum epirensis*, which is very numerous in

southern Greece; as well as the record by Sláma & Slámová (1996: 135) for Kerkira (Corfu) Is. ("Aj. Mathaeos").

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum valonense* Pic, 1917**

- ? *Dorcadion fuscifrons* Chevrolat, 1882: 60 - "Albania".
- Dorcadion femoratum* v. *valonense* Pic, 1917b: 6 - "Albanie occidentale".
- Dorcadion valonense* Apfelbeck, 1923: 145, 148, 149 - "Valona, Šen Thanas und Pašaliman in Albanien"; Heyrovský, 1967: 579, 609 - Albania, "Dajti, Shkall Prisk, 850 m", "Dajti, Westhang, 1100 m"; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 47 - "Tirane; Mal i Dajt".
- Dorcadion* (s. str.) *apfelbecki* Winkler, 1929: 1188 - "Albanien"; Schatzmayr, 1943: 134 - "Lushnja".
- Dorcadion apfelbecki* a. *jedličkai* Heyrovský, 1937: 89, 91 - "Albanien: Maja e Konigskol, Seraqin".
- Dorcadion etruscum* a. *valonense*, Heyrovský, 1937: 89 - "Kara Ali Bey".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) valonense* m. *grisellum* Breuning, 1946: 115 - "Valonia, Albanie".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) valonense* m. *femorale* Breuning, 1946, 115 - "Argyrokastron, Albanie".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) valonense* m. *apicesignatum* Breuning, 1946: 115 - "Argyrokastron, Albanie".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) etruscum* m. *fuscifrons*, Breuning, 1962: 347, part. - "Abruzzen; Albanien".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) valonense*, Breuning, 1962: 350 - "Südliches Albanien: Valona, Kosuf Planina"; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 217 - "Tirana, c/o Facoltà di Agraria", "Monte Dajti (Tirana prov.)".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) albosuturale*, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 218 - Albania: "Ardenica" [40°49'N 19°35'E].
- Dorcadion albosuturale*, Heyrovský, 1967: 579, 610 - Albania; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 47 - "Erseke; 5 km SW Kolonje".
- Dorcadion lugubre*, Heyrovský, 1967: 579, 610 - Albania, "Tomor, Kloster Abbas-Ali, 1800 m"; Siering, Shumka & Rothe, 2016: 47 - "Küste; Orikum", "Küste; SE Orikum; Dukat Fshat und Umland", "P.K. Llogara".
- Dorcadion etruscum*, Heyrovský, 1967: 579, part. - "Albanien, Griechenland".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) lugubre*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 249 - Albania.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) albosuturale*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 243, part. - Albania, Greece; 2010b: 233, part. - "Albania, Greece, Macedonia: near Ochrid lake; Galiëica National Park"; 2020: 340, part. - Albania, Greece.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) valonense*, Danilevsky, 2010a: 254 - Albania; 2020: 359 - Albania.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) etruscum*, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 217 - "Beart, passo circa 22 km sud Beart".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum*, Plewa et al., 2018: 181 - "County Korçë: Radanj at Gërmenj, 1060 m a.s.l.", "County Vlorë: Llogara, Mts Çikës, 1200 m a.s.l.".

Type locality. The taxon was described from “Albanie occidentale”, but exact type locality - Valona (now Vlorë) is evident after the name of the taxon.

The oldest name *Dorcadion fuscifrons* Chevrolat, 1882 allegedly described from “Albania”, could be connected with other taxon. Breuning (1962) supposed its type locality as “Abruzzen”, and so it could be a synonym of *D. etruscum* (Rossi, 1790).

Rather variable taxon; body black; 1st antennal joint and legs from totally black to reddish or dark-red; pronotum without central depression; with smooth ventral line, in males with poorly developed white central stripe, which could be rather distinct or totally absent; pronotal puncturation usually more or less scattered or very dense, irregular and conjugated (inside one population); elytra densely punctated; always glabrous in males; sutural white line often totally absent or hardly visible, sometimes more or less distinct; dark elytral pubescence always absent in males; females androchromal or autochromal with totally pubescent elytra, with poorly developed humeral and dorsal greyish stripes; body length in males: 12.2-14.0 mm, width: 4.7-5.4 mm; body length in females: 14.5-16.2 mm, body width: 6.2-7.0 mm.

Material: 2 males, 2 females, Albania, Vlorë, Liogora Pass, 1025 m, 29.4.1993, W. Heinz - MD; 2 males, 2 females, Albania, Tirana, Krraba Pass, 800 m, 29.4.1993, W. Heinz - MD; 1 female, Albania, Vlorë distr., near Dukati, 450 m, 11.5.1995, Golovach, Stoev, Petrov - MD; 7 female, 3 females, S Albania, Vlorë County, 7.5 km SW Vlorë, 5 km S Kanine vill., Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45''N, 19°31'10.09''E, 810 m, 5.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 3 males, 1 female, Vlorë, 4.5 km S Kaninë, 40°23'57.34''N, 19°31'5.06''E, 757 m, 5.5.2021, A.I. Gubin - AG; 1 male, S Albania, Gjirokastrë County, Gjirokastrë distr., near Saraqinisht vill., Lunxherise Mts., 40°7'2.61''N, 20°13'37.68''E, 900 m, 7.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 2 males, S Albania, Gjirokastrë County, 3 km E Labovë e Vogël vill., Llofiz Mts., 40°11'56.30''N, 20°10'37.65''E, 1289 m, 8.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 3 males, Albania, Gjirokastrë county, 13 km NNE Gjirokastrë, Llofiz Mts. Cajup Field, 41°11'59''N, 20°10'39''E, 1300 m, 8.5.2021, O. Pak leg. - ML;

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1 male, 1 female, Girokastër, 1.6 km N Sarakinishtë, Lunxherise Mts., 40°7'8.07''N, 20°13'33''E, 916 m, 8.5.2021, A.I. Gubin - AG; 28 males, 12 females, SW Albania, Vlorë County, 7.5 km SW Vlorë, 5 km S Kanine vill., Lungar Mts., 40°23'37.45''N, 19°31'10.09''E, 810 m, 16.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS; 1 male, Albania, 7 km SE Vlorë, Kanine vill., 700 m, 16.5.2021, O. Pak - MD; 63 males, 14 females, Albania, Vlorë County, 7 km SW Vlorë, Kanine vill. env. Lungar Mts., 770 m, 16.5.2021, I. Plushch leg. - IP; 4 male, 2 females, Vlorë, 4.5 km S Kaninë, 40°23'57.34''N, 19°31'5.06''E, 757 m, 16.5.2021, A.I. Gubin - AG; 2 males, SW Albania, Vlorë County, Llogara National Park, Maja e Thanasit Mts., 40°11'52.72''N, 19°35'32.38''E, 1037 m, 17.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - YuS.

Distribution. Whole territory of Albania, with the exception of eastern part in Mal-i-That environs, Prespa National Park. The taxon penetrates to Greece.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) etruscum bravardi Pic, 1916

Dorcadion bravardi Pic, 1916: 22 - "Environs de Salonique"; 1917b: 2 - "Environs de Salonique"; Heyrovský, 1967: 579, 610, part. - "Mazedonien, Albanien".

Dorcadion (s. str.) *bravardi*, Winkler, 1929: 1191 - "Saloniki".

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) valonense m. *albosuturale* Breuning, 1946: 115 - "Mal-i-Dhatit, Albanie" (unavailable name).

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) albosuturale Breuning, 1962: 351, part. - "Albanien: Mal-i-that; Thessalien: Elassona; Argyrokastorn" **syn. nov.**

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) bravardi, Breuning, 1962: 352 - "Albanien: Mal-i-that".

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) bravardi, Özdikmen, 2010: 430, part. - Albania, Greece; Danilevsky, 2010a: 244, part. - Albania, Greece, Macedonia; 2020: 342, part. - Albania, Greece, Macedonia.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) albosuturale, Danilevsky, 2010b: 233, part. - "Albania, Greece, Macedonia: near Ochrid lake; Galiëica National Park".

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) etruscum bravardi, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 217 - "Albania: Mal i That".

Type locality. The taxon was described from Greece ("Environs de Salonique"), but according to Breuning (1962), it was wrong record and the real type locality must be accepted as Albania: Mal-i-That.

Body smaller, black; 1st antennal joint and legs dark-red; pronotum regularly convex, without central depression, with white central line, pronotal puncturation relatively regular, very dense;

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elytra in males less variable, glabrous densely punctated, sutural white line always present; dark elytral pubescence absent; females androchromal with totally pubescent elytra, with poorly developed humeral and dorsal greyish stripes; body length in males: 11.4-12.1 mm, width: 4.1-4.3 mm; body length in females: 13.5-15.2 mm, body width: 5.8-6.1 mm.

Material. 3 males, 2 females, SE Albania, Korçë County, 3 km S Leskë, Prespa National Park, Maja Kulles Mts., 40°45'3.38"N, 20°53'7.49"E, 1055 m, 11.5.2021, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - ML, YuS; 1 male, Albania, Korçë county, Thate Mts., Bregas vill. env., 40°47'39"N, 20°49'32"E, 1325 m, 10.5.2021 O. Pak leg. - ML.

Distribution. South-eastern Albania, Mal-i-That environs, Prespa National Park, penetrates to Greece and North Makedonia.

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REFERENCES

- Aistleitner E., Lencina Gutiérrez J.L. & Adlbauer K. 2015. Fragmenta entomofaunistica XIX. Faunistische Notizen zu Arten der Gattung *Iberodorcadion* Breuning, 1943 auf der Iberischen Halbinsel sowie Streudaten der *Dorcadiini* diverser Provenienz (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae). - Entomofauna. Zeitschrift für Entomologie, Ansfelden. 36 (41): 537-548, 1 fig.
- Angelini F. 2020. Contribution to the knowledge of beetles (Insecta Coleoptera) of some protected areas of Apulia, Basilicata and Calabria (Italy). - Biodiversity Journal. 11 (1): 85-254. DOI: 10.31396/Biodiv.Jour.2020.11.1.85.254
- Apfelbeck K. 1923: [new taxon]. In: Breit J. Beitrag zur Kenntnis der *Dorcadion*-Arten des Balkans. Wiener Entomologische Zeitung. 40 (5-10): 145-149.
- Aurivillius C. 1922. Cerambycidae: Lamiinae I. Pars 73. In: Schenkling S. (ed.). Coleopterorum Catalogus. Volumen XXIII. Cerambycidae II. [1921]. Berlin: W. Junk, 322 pp.
- Baviera C., Bellavista M., Altadonna G., Turrisi G.F., Bella S., Muscarella C. & Sparacio I. 2017. The Cerambycidae (Coleoptera: Chrysomeloidea) of

M.A. Lazarev

- Sicily: recent records and updated checklist. - *Atti della Accademia Peloritana dei Pericolanti. Classe di Scienze Fisiche, Matematiche e Naturali.* 95 (1): 1-79.
- Behne L. & Gaedike H. 2013. Katalog der in den Sammlungen des Senckenberg Deutschen Entomologischen Instituts aufbewahrten Typen - Coleoptera: Cerambycidae. - *Contributions to Entomology: Beiträge zur Entomologie.* 63 (1): 169-198.
- Braun W. 1978. Die Dorcadienausbeute der Forschungsreisen von W. Heinz 1963-1977. Faunistische Aufstellung, Beschreibung einer neuen Unterart und Bemerkungen zur Systematik wenig bekannter Arten (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - *Nachrichtenblatt der Bayerischen Entomologen.* 27 (6): 101-116.
- Breit J. 1923. Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Dorcadion-Arten des Balkans. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung.* 40 (5-10): 145-149.
- Breuning S. 1942. Neue Art von Dorcadion aus Südtalien. - *Bolletino del Laboratorio di Zoologia generale e agraria della Facoltà Agraria in Portici.* 32: 125-129.
- Breuning S. 1943. Nouveaux Cérambycides paléarctiques (1re note). - *Miscellanea Entomologica.* 40 (9): 89-104.
- Breuning S. 1946. Nouvelles formes de Dorcadion (Col. Cerambycidae). - *Miscellanea Entomologica.* 43 (8): 91-132, 2 figs.
- Breuning S. 1956. Quelques nouvelles formes du genre Dorcadion Dalm. *Longicornia.* 3: 723-728, 1 fig. Paul Lechevalier, Paris.
- Breuning S. 1958. 1. Lieferung, pp: 1-48. In: S.Breuning, 1958-1969. *Catalogue des Lamiaires du Monde (Col. Céramb.).* Tutzing bei München, Verlag des Museums G. Frey: 1069 pp.
- Breuning S. 1962. Revision der Dorcadionini (Col. Ceramb.). - *Abhandlungen und Berichte aus dem staatlichen Museum für Tierkunde in Dresden.* 27: 1-666, 33 figs.
- Breuning S. 1964. Quatre nouvelles espèces du genre Dorcadion Dalm. (Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - *Bolletino dell'Associazione Romana di Entomologia.* 19 (3-4): 31-32, 1 pl.
- Breuning S. 1966. Une nouvelle espèce du genre Dorcadion de Grèce (Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - *Bollettino dell'Associazione romana di entomologia.* 21 (1): 4-5, pl. II.
- Breuning S. 1969. Quelques formes nouvelles du genre Dorcadion Dalm. de Grèce (Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - *Bollettino dell'Associazione Romana di Entomologia.* 24 (2): 42.
- Breuning S. 1975. Descriptions de Dorcadiens nouveaux d'Anatolie (Coleoptera Lamiinae). - *Bulletin de la Société Entomologique de Mulhouse [janvier-février-mars 1975]:* 10.
- Brullé A.G. 1832-1836. *Expédition scientifique de Morée. Section des Sciences Physiques. Tome III. - 1.re Partie. Zoologie. Deuxième Section. - Des animaux articulés.* F.G. Levrault, Paris. 3 (1/2): 1-400, 52 pls. (pages 289-400 issued in 1833; plates in 1832-1836)
- Chevrolat L.A.A. 1882. *Espèces nouvelles de Longicornes européens et circa-*

M.A. Lazarev

- méditerranéens et Remarques diverses. - *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France*, Paris. (6) 2: 57-64.
- Contarini E. 2014. Elenco faunistico commentato (check-list) dei Cerambicidi (Coleoptera Xylophytophaga) del Parco Naturale della Vena del Gesso romagnola. - *Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*. 40: 39-65.
- Danilevsky M.L. 2010a. tribe Dorcadionini, pp. 241-264. - In I. Lobl & A. Smetana (ed.): *Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera*, Vol. 6. Stenstrup: Apollo Books, 924 pp. DOI: 10.1163/9789004260917_001
- Danilevsky M.L. 2010b. Additions and corrections to the new Catalogue of Palaearctic Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) edited by I. Löbl and A. Smetana, 2010. - *Russian Entomological Journal*. 19 (3): 215-239.
- Danilevsky M.L. 2014. Two new subspecies of *Dorcadion aethiops* (Scopoli, 1763) from Bulgaria (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - *Humanity space. International almanac*. 3 (2): 251-254, 5 figs.
- Danilevsky M.L. 2020 (ed.). *Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera*, vol. 6 (1), Chrysomeloidea I (Vesperidae, Disteniidae, Cerambycidae). Revised and updated edition. Leiden / Boston: Brill. i-xxii, 1-712. DOI: 10.1163/9789004440333
- Depoli G. 1926. I Dorcadion italiani. - *Memorie della Società Entomologica Italiana*. 5: 5-34.
- Fabbri R.A. & Hernández J.M. 1996. Il ciclo biologico di *Dorcadion Dalman*, 1817 della Romagna a confronto con quello di altri *Dorcadionini* Thomson, 1860 spagnoli e asiatici (Insecta, Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - *Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*. 5: 19-40.
- Heyrovský L. 1937. Druhý příspěvek k poznání albánských tesariků. = Zweiter Beitrag zur Kenntnis der albanischen Cerambyciden (Col. Ceramb.). - *Ěasopis Ěeskoslovenské společnosti entomologické*. 31: 132-137.
- Heyrovský L. 1962. Zwei neue *Dorcadion*-Arten aus der Balkanhalbinsel. - *Bulgarische Akademie der Wissenschaften. Mitteilungen des zoologischen Institutes und Museums, Sofia*. 12: 225-226.
- Kraatz G. 1873. Die Käfer Europas. Nach der Natur beschrieben von Dr. G. Kraatz im Anschluss an die Käfer Europa's von Dr. H.C. Küster. - In Küster, 1873. *Die Käfer Europas nach der Natur beschrieben*. 29: 1-101.
- Küster H.C. 1847. Die Käfer Europa's. Nach der Natur beschrieben. Mit Beiträgen mehrerer Entomologen. - Nürnberg, Bauer & Raspe. 10: No 1-100, 3 pls.
- Küster H.C. 1852. Die Käfer Europa's. Nach der Natur beschrieben. Mit Beiträgen mehrerer Entomologen. - Nürnberg, Bauer & Raspe. 25: No 1-100, 2 pls.
- Luna M. & Rapuzzi P. 2016. Contributo alla conoscenza dei Longicorni dell'Appennino Umbro nella provincia di Perugia. - *Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*. 43: 163-196.
- Migliaccio E., Georgiev G., Gashtarov V. 2007. An annotated list of Bulgarian Cerambycids with special view on the rarest species and endemics (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - *Lambillionea. Revue internationale d'entomologie*. 107 (1), supplément 1: 1-79.
- Mikšić R. & Korpíč M. 1985. Cerambycidae Jugoslavije, III. - *Académie des*

M.A. Lazarev

- Sciences de Bosnie-Herzégovine, Sarajevo. Monographie. 62 (5): 1-148.
- Önalp B. 1990. Systematic researches on *Dorcadion Dalman*, 1817 species in Turkey (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae: Lamiinae) I. H. Ü. - Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi. 5: 57-102.
- Oertzen E. 1886. Verzeichnis der Coleopteren Griechenlands und Cretas. - Berliner Entomologische Zeitschrift. 30: 189-293.
- Özdikmen H. 2010. The Turkish *Dorcadiini* with zoogeographical remarks (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lamiinae). - Munis Entomology & Zoology. 5 (2): 380-498.
- Özdikmen H. & Hasbenli A. 2004a. Contribution to the knowledge of longhorned beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Turkey, Subfamily Lamiinae. - Journal of the Entomological Research Society. 6 (2): 25-49.
- Papini G. & Tassi F. Elenco di Coleotteri raccolti nel Parco Nazionale d'Abruzzo. - Bolletino dell'Associazione Romana di Entomologia. 19 (3-4): 34-36.
- Pesarini C. & Sabbadini A. 2004. Ricerche sui *Dorcadiini* di Grecia. I. Le specie del Peloponneso (Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - Atti della Società Italiana di Scienze Naturali e del Museo Civico di Storia Naturale in Milano. 145 (1): 133-153, 25 figs.
- Pesarini C. & Sabbadini A. 2007. Ricerche sui *Dorcadiini* di Grecia. II. Le specie della Grecia centromeridionale e quelle del gruppo di *Dorcadion kozanii* (Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - Atti della Società Italiana di Scienze Naturali e del Museo Civico di Storia Naturale in Milano. 148 (1): 35-83.
- Pesarini C. & Sabbadini A. 2010. Ricerche sui *Dorcadionini* di Grecia. IV. Le specie della Macedonia e della Tracia (Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - Atti della Società Italiana di Scienze Naturali e del Museo Civico di Storia Naturale in Milano. 151 (2): 179-216.
- Petruzzello L. & Migliorini A. 2019. Contributo alla conoscenza dei Longicorni della provincia di Piacenza (Insecta: Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna. 49: 141-186.
- Pic M. 1916. Notes diverses, descriptions et diagnoses (Suite.). - L'Échange, Revue Linnéenne. 32 (378): 21-23.
- Pic M. 1917a. Notes diverses, descriptions et diagnoses (Suite.). - L'Échange, Revue Linnéenne. 33 (381): 9-11.
- Pic M. 1917b. Notes diverses et diagnoses. - Matériaux pour servir à l'étude des Longicornes. 10 (2): 3-10.
- Pic M. 1926a. Notes diverses, descriptions et diagnoses (Suite.). - L'Échange, Revue Linnéenne. 42 (423): 1-2.
- Pic M. 1926b. Notes diverses, descriptions et diagnoses (Suite.). - L'Échange, Revue Linnéenne. 42 (426): 13-14.
- Pic M. 1932. Notes diverses, nouveautés (Suite.). - L'Échange, Revue Linnéenne. 48 (447): 17-18.
- Plewa R., Łoś K., Górski P. 2011. New data on the distribution, biology and behavior of some longhorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Greece. - Elateridium. 5: 232-247.
- Plewa R., Górski P., Gazurek T., Tytkowski S., Szewczyk M. & Byk A. 2018. New Data on the Occurrence of Longhorn Beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)

M.A. Lazarev

- in Albania. - *Acta zoologica Bulgaria*. 70 (2): 179-183.
- Rapuzzi P. & Sama G. 2006. Cerambycidae nuovi o interessanti per la fauna di Sicilia (Insecta Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - *Quaderni di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*. 23: 157-172.
- Rapuzzi P. & Sama G. 2012. Contributo alla conoscenza dei Cerambycidae di Albania (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - *Atti del Museo Civico di Storia Naturale Trieste*. 55: 181-234.
- Rossi P. 1790. Fauna Etrusca, sistens Insecta, quae in provinciis Florentina et Pisana praesertim collegit. - *Thomae Masi, Liburni*. 1: iii-xxii + 1-272.
- Sakalian V., Migliaccio E., Tassi F., Doychev D. & Georgiev G. 2020. New and interesting records of jewel and longhorn beetles from Abruzzo, Lazio and Molise National Park, Italy (Coleoptera: Buprestidae and Cerambycidae). - *Fragmenta Entomologica, Roma*. 52 (1): 63-66.
- Sakalian V., Migliaccio E., Tassi F. & Georgiev G. 2021. A checklist and areography of Buprestidae, Vesperidae and Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) in Abruzzo, Lazio and Molise National Park, Italy. - *Travaux du Muzeul de Istoria Naturala «Grigore Antipa», Bucarest*. 64 (2): 35-60, 1 fig.
- Sama G. 1984. Materiali per una Fauna dei Cerambycidae d'Italia. III. Revisione dei tipi della collezione P. Rossi. - *Giornale Italiano di Entomologia, Cremona*. 2 (6): 1-6.
- Sama G. 1988. Fauna d'Italia. Vol. XXV. Coleoptera, Cerambycidae. Catalogo topografico e sinonimico. Bologna: 216 pp.
- Sama G., Rapuzzi P. & Kairouz A. 2010. Catalogue commenté des Cerambycidae du Liban. An annotated catalogue of the Cerambycidae of Lebanon (Insecta Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - *Quaderni di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*. 30: 131-201, 26 figs.
- Sama G. & Rapuzzi P. 2011. Una nuova Checklist dei Cerambycidae d'Italia (Insecta Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - *Quaderni di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*. 32: 121-164.
- Sama G. & Schurmann P. 1980. Coleotteri Cerambycidi di Sicilia. - *Animalia*. 7 (1/3): 189-230.
- Sláma M. & Slámová J. 1996. Contribution to the recognition of Greek and Yugoslavian longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - *Bioscosme Mésogéen, Nice*. (1995) 12 (4): 117-143.
- Steiner S. 2003. Vorbereitende Untersuchungen zu einer Revision der Tribus Dorcadionini (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lamiinae) in Griechenland, Teil I. - *Acta Entomologica Slovenica*. 11, 2: 137-158.
- Usvelli A. 2003. 25 anni di ricerche entomologiche a Badia della Valle, Marradi (Firenze). - *Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*. 18:57-62.
- Winkler A. 1929. *Phytophaga-Cerambycidae. Catalogus Coleopterorum Regionis Palaearcticae*, Wien. 10: 1135-1226.

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**A new *Litargus* species from Australia
(Coleoptera: Mycetophagidae)**

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Key words: taxonomy, new species, Coleoptera, Mycetophagidae, *Litargus*, Australia, Queensland.

Abstract: A new species *Litargus* (*Litargosomus*) *suturalis* **sp. nov.** from Australia, Queensland is described, illustrated and compared.

Introduction

The genus *Litargus* Erichson, 1846 can be divided into the following 4 subgenera: *Alitargus* Casey, 1900 including 3 species, *Litargosomus* Motschulsky, 1858 including 21 species, *Litargus* Erichson, 1846 including 16 species, *Paralitargus* Casey, 1900 including 1 species and 21 species as incertae sedis (Háva 2022, 2023). Only one cosmopolitan species is known from Australia as an introduced species (Lawrence 1987, Lawrence & Ślipiński 2013, Hagstrum & Subramanyam 2009, Háva 2022).

During the determination of some unidentified material deposited in Naturhistorisches Museum, Wien I a new species from Australia, Queensland east found, which is described below.

Material and Methods

The type material is deposited in the following collection:

NHMW - Naturhistorisches Museum, Wien, Austria
(M. Seidel).

The size of the beetles or of their body parts can be useful in the species recognition and thus, the following measurements were made:

total length (TL) - linear distance from anterior margin of head to apex of elytra.

elytral width (EW) - maximum linear transverse distance.

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The specimen of the presently described species are provided with red, printed label with text as follows: “HOLOTYPE *Litargus* (*Litargosomus*) *suturalis* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2023”.

Results

Litargus (*Litargosomus*) *suturalis* sp. nov.

Figs. 1-2

Description. Female. Body measurements TL 2.1 mm, EW 1.1 mm; oblong-oval, subparallel-sided; weakly convex dorsally, weakly glossy; brown on dorsal and ventral surfaces, covered with short, light brown recumbent setation.

Head brown, with dense and coarse punctures; covered by light brown, recumbent setation; labrum brown; eyes prominent laterally in dorsal view, coarsely faceted and slightly emarginate near antennal insertions; antennae with 11 antennomeres (but antennomeres 10-11 missing), entirely light brown with brown setation, antennal club with three antennomeres; palpi brown, apical maxillary palpomere large, cylindrical.

Pronotum brown, convex dorsally, rugose, with large and dense punctures, covered with light brown recumbent setation; widest at middle, gradually narrowed anteriorly and posteriorly; anterior margin slightly arcuate; sides roundly arcuate; basal margin sinuate, without short and circular grooves on subbasal parts.

Scutellum broadly triangular, with short recumbent light brown setation.

Elytra brown with dark brown suture and humeri, without colour yellowish patterns, covered by light brown recumbent setation, elongate, subparallel-sided, narrowed from apical 1/4 to apex (Figs. 1-2). Epipleuron brown, covered with light brown recumbent setation. Mesometaventrite brown, with light brown recumbent setation. Prosternal process broad.

Legs entirely brown with light brown spines, covered with yellow recumbent setation. Tibiae with long brown spines apically.

Abdominal visible ventrites brown, covered with light brown recumbent setation. Pygidium brown, covered with light brown recumbent setation.

Male. Unknown.

Figs. 1-2. *Litargus (Litargosomus) suturalis* **sp. nov.** (holotype): 1 - body, dorsal aspect; 2- elytra, dorsal aspect.

Differential diagnosis. The new species differs from the introduced species *Litargus balteatus* LeConte, 1856 by the elytral colour without yellowish spots; from other known Oriental species, it differs by the colour of elytra (elytra brown with dark brown suture and humeri).

Type material. Holotype, female, Australia, QLD, Cape Tribulation Daintre N.P, Turpentine Road, 120 m, 8.11.1996, L. Hendrich leg. - NHMW.

Etymology. Named according to dark brown elytral suture.

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REFERENCES

- Hagstrum D.W. & Subramanyam B. 2009. Stored-product Insect resource. St. Paul: AACC International, i-viii + 509 pp.
- Háva J. 2022: World Catalogue of Mycetophagidae (Coleoptera: Tenebrionoidea). - Studies and Reports. Taxonomical Series. 18 (2): 287-331.
- Háva J. 2023: A new *Litargus* species from Thailand (Coleoptera: Mycetophagidae). - *Munis Entomology & Zoology*. 18 (2). (in press).
- Lawrence J.F. 1987: Notes on the classification of some Australian Tenebrionoidea (Coleoptera). - *Journal of the Australian Entomological Society*. 26: 361-362.
- Lawrence J.F. & Ślipiński A. 2013: Australian Beetles. Volume 1. Morphology, classification and keys. Collingwood: CSIRO, 561 pp.

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